

Survey on fashion consumption trends of Vietnamese young people

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ABSTRACT

Young people today are increasingly active and always like to try new trends in many fields. Especially in the field of fashion, mixing clothes is applied boldly and extremely diversely by young people. A fashion trend is an innovation in style that is adopted by a group of people at a certain time and area. Trends are formed based on factors: people, acceptance, time, and place. The article surveyed 300 young people of generation Z in Vietnam, the results showed that the number of fashion enthusiasts is very large, 70.7%, personal preference factors are the biggest influence on people's fashion choices. According to the survey subjects, online fashion shopping is chosen by young people at a large rate. KOL (Key Opinion Leader) currently plays a very important role in building and developing fashion brands. Vietnamese fashion accounts for the highest proportion in choosing fashion products associated with product origin. The survey shows that they are most interested in "Product style and design", "A neat appearance" ... The article also mentions some opinions about fashion and money that young people are willing and able to pay for per month. From there, the research team launched several exchanges and discussions with Vietnamese fashion businesses to meet consumer needs and build brands in the market.

KEYWORDS

Consumption trend, fashion, Vietnamese young people

1. RAISING THE ISSUES

Fashion is like breathing in the lives of young people. Especially in today's modern and integrated era, fashion styles are innovated by young people every day and do not follow any standards or stereotypes. (heritagevietnamairlines.com, 2022)

Fashion rotates constantly over time. The dynamism - freedom - liberality - creativity - genderlessness of generation Z has played a role in "reviving" many trends that once disappeared. (coupletx.com, 2022)

Dynamic, trendy, liberal, free - these are the keywords to describe the dressing style of today's youth. Gen Z fashion trends are not necessarily completely new items, but rather the trendy and bold combination of seemingly old items to create the most attractive style. (mialala.vn, 2023)

Young people are increasingly active and always like to try new trends in many fields. Especially in the field of fashion, mixing clothes is widely applied by young people. (Thanh Du, 2023)

In order to learn about the fashion trends of Vietnamese youth, the research team developed a survey to collect information about generation Z fashion trends for young people born in 1995-2010, with the following aspects: Take into consideration: The importance of fashion for young people; Fashion choice trends of young people in modern life; The amount of money young people are willing to spend on fashion shopping; The trend of combining multiple channels in the fashion shopping process of young people; Consider some perspectives such as the fact that young people often spend more freely thanks to combined incentives and entertainment; Favorite fashion brands; The influence of Beauty Bloggers/KOLs on users' choice to buy fashion products; Fashion style; Origin of the product; Factors affecting the choice of fashion products; Aspect to consider when buying fashion products; And also some notes when consuming fashion products...

2. OVERVIEW OF YOUNG PEOPLE'S FASHION

2.1. Fashion

Fashion is a concept that has become an indispensable part of modern life. It is not simply about clothes, accessories or dressing style, but also a field of art, expressing each person's personality and style. The role of fashion in modern life is not only limited to protecting the body from external influences but also has a profound influence on many aspects of human life, from economics to society, psychology, and spirit. (Jelly Nguyen, 2023)

Fashion can be understood as a habit, or a certain style related to clothes, shoes, or fashion accessories. In addition, fashion is sometimes not just a trend that someone follows, it is simply the way we choose our daily outfits. Fashion has become an important part of life. (Zofal, 2021)

According to Kaiser, Susan B. (2019) Fashion is an aesthetic expression popular at a particular time, place, and context using clothing, footwear, lifestyle, accessories, makeup, hairstyles, and body proportion. Unlike trends, which often involve a particular aesthetic expression and often last less than a season, fashion is a particular expression, supported by the fashion industry, that is often associated with seasons and collection (Kawamura, Yuniija, (2005).

Fashion is the style and trend of clothing, accessories, hairstyles, and makeup that people follow at a particular time. It is expressed through the selection, combination and arrangement of clothes, accessories, shoes, and other elements to create a physical appearance that is beautiful, harmonious and suitable for different situations like work, parties, special events or everyday activities. (Jelly Nguyen, 2023)

Thus, fashion is not only about wearing beautiful clothes, but also reflects each person's style, personality, and ego. It changes according to time, place, culture, trends and the mood of the wearer. Fashion has a strong interaction with the fashion industry, economy, society, culture, and

environment. It is influenced by designers, fashion stars, catwalks, technology, environmental sustainability, and other factors.

2.2. The importance of fashion for young people

According to Zofal (2021) fashion help us with: (i) A neat appearance; (ii) The most authentic language of the wearer; (iii) Respect for yourself and others; (iv) Fashion makes you confident; (v) Hobbies and passions.

According to Jelly Nguyen (2023), fashion is not just a style of dressing, but also an indispensable part of modern human life. The role of fashion in modern life has now become an important factor, influencing the way people express themselves, interact with each other and express their egos.

Fashion is how young people can express themselves. Through clothing, accessories and makeup, young people can express their style, personality, interests, and opinions. Fashion is a non-verbal means of communication, helping young people create their own image, express their own personality, and attract the attention of those around them.

Fashion is an important factor in social interaction. Through the way they wear clothes and accessories, young people can position themselves within a social group, identify themselves or differentiate themselves from other groups, and express their status, class, wealth, or profession. Fashion is also a tool to create social relationships, because it can make an impression, create common ground or be a topic to start a conversation and enhance communication between young people.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Desk research methods. The research team reviewed documents on opinions about fashion, favorite fashion brands, favorite online and offline fashion shopping channels, fashion styles, and fashion origins that are often chosen by young people, the amount of money willing to pay monthly for fashion, factors that influence the choice of fashion products, and aspects to consider when choosing fashion products.

Data collection methods. The research team developed a survey form on aspects compiled on the basis of desk research to conduct a sociological investigation on fashion consumption trends of young people of generation Z (born 1995-2012) in Vietnam.

The research team collected data based on the convenience sampling method and the “snowball” method - the method of finding the next subject based on the suggestion or introduction of the subject just surveyed. The survey was built on Google driver and was conducted as a pilot survey for 10 young people who are fashionistas. Based on the comments of the respondents, the research team completed the survey and sent survey

link(https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSckbvFpmGsf5aduR0cFw_pRpMtQspQKJYcgr-RIki_5fBurQ/viewform) to Vietnamese young people of generation Z through social media such as Facebook, Zalo, Email...The total number of survey questionnaires collected and analyzed was 300.

Survey data analysis methods. Survey data were compiled and statistically compiled using Excel software, thereby analyzing, and demonstrating the research problem.

Some contents in the survey are designed on a 5-likert scale, including: 1. Very uninterested; 2. Uninterested; 3. Normal; 4. Interested; 5. Very interested. The research team collects survey data and calculates the average value of the aspects included in the survey. Therefore, when evaluating the level of perception of the aspects, the research team calculated:

Distance value = (Maximum - Minimum) / n = (5-1)/5 = 0.8

The average value of the calculated aspects if within the range:

- + 1.00 - 1.80: Very uninterested.
- + 1.81 - 2.60: Uninterested.
- + 2.61 - 3.40: Normal.
- + 3.41 - 4.20: Interested.
- + 4.21 - 5.00: Very interested.

4. FASHION CONSUMPTION TRENDS OF VIETNAMESE YOUNG PEOPLE: PERSPECTIVE FROM SURVEY RESULTS

4.1. Description of survey objects

Figure 1. Gender of survey participants

Source: Survey results

Of the 300 people participating in the survey, there were 174 females (accounting for 58%), 119 male (accounting for 40%) and 7 people did not want to be specific (2%).

Figure 2. Educational level of survey subjects

Source: Survey results

Of the 300 survey participants, 26 people (accounting for 8.7%) have completed high school; 11 people (3.7%) have completed college; 261 people (87%) have graduated from university; 2 people (accounting for 0.7%) are working and are not students.

Figure 3. Living area of survey subjects

Source: Survey results

Of the 300 people participating in the survey, 202 people (accounting for 67%) live in the inner-city area; 98 people (accounting for 33%) live in suburban areas.

4.2. Fashion consumption trends of Vietnamese young people

Figure 4. Percentage of survey respondents who are “Fashionistas.”

Source: Survey results.

With 300 survey participants, when asked about whether it was “*Fashionistas*”, the results show that: 212 people (accounting for 71%) answered that they are fashionistas, large proportion; 88 people (accounting for 29%) answered that they are not fashionistas.

Figure 5. Perspectives on fashion

Source: Survey results

Results of a survey of fashion opinions of 212 people (fashionistas) showed:

72.6% Understand the body shape and choose clothes that “show off the beauty and hide the ugliness”.

53.3% Not pay too much attention to branded products.

50.5% Fashion inspiration is everywhere.

57.5% Prioritize clothes that are both comfortable and still attractive.

73.6% Choose clothes that make them confident and comfortable.

26.4% Fashion choices to “FLEX” (show off prosperity, individuality, and style).

The results show many different perspectives on fashion. Fashion also brings many other meanings to people’s lives from past to present. Fashion helps us become impressive, attractive, and always score points with the opposite person.

Figure 6. Favorite fashion brand

Source: Survey results

Favorite brands are ranked in order from top to bottom as follows:

Nike: 130 people (accounting for 43.3%) interested in this brand. According to survey results, this is the most favorite brand.

Louis Vuitton: 106 people (accounting for 35.3%) interested in this brand.

Adidas: 105 people (accounting for 35%) interested in this brand.

Gucci: 99 people (accounting for 33%) interested in this brand.

Canifa: 98 people (accounting for 32.7%) interested in this brand.

Li-ning: 87 people (accounting for 29%) interested in this brand.

Dirty Coins: 69 people (accounting for 23%) interested in this brand.

Bobui: 63 people (accounting for 21%) interested in this brand.

MLB: 63 people (accounting for 21%) interested in this brand.

Ivy Moda: 61 people (accounting for 20.3%) interested in this brand.

Drew: 61 people (accounting for 20.3%) interested in this brand.

Coolmate: 53 people (accounting for 17.7%) interested in this brand.

ADLV: 52 people (accounting for 17.3%) interested in this brand.

Yame: 43 people (accounting for 14.3%) interested in this brand.

5The way: 43 people (accounting for 14.3%) interested in this brand.

Local Brands: TSUN, SWE... 41 people (accounting for 13.7%) are interested in this brand.
Human Made: 38 people (accounting for 12.7%) interested in this brand.
Tingoan: 35 people (accounting for 11.7%) interested in this brand.
Anti socialsocial club: 30 people (accounting for 10%) interested in this brand.
Off-White: 30 people (accounting for 10%) interested in this brand.
Bape: 20 people (accounting for 6.7%) interested in this brand.
Khác: 20 people (accounting for 6.7%) interested in other brands.

Box 1. The story of Nike and its “empire” in the fashion industry

Nike is known as a “giant” in the sports fashion industry, as all Nike products are always highly appreciated for their beautiful design, high quality and meeting user trends.

In addition to the historical story of the Nike brand, this brand also stands out with the product lines they develop. Currently, Nike’s product lines are quite diverse with many items.

The journey of building the brand of this group also went through many storms and challenges to get to where it is today. With quality products and effective advertising strategies, Nike Group has affirmed its irreplaceable position in the domestic and international fashion market.

Source: *icheck.com.vn* (2022)

Figure 7. Fashion shopping channel

Source: Survey results

Regarding fashion shopping channels, the survey results are arranged in order from the most chosen channel to the least chosen channel:

Online shopping: 224 people (accounting for 74.7%) shop for fashion products from online stores.

At the shops: 195 people (accounting for 65%) buy fashion products from other diverse shops.

Shopping malls: 167 people (accounting for 55.7%) shop for fashion products from shopping malls.

Brand’s official stores: 160 people (accounting for 53.3%) shop for fashion products from the brand’s official stores.

Distributors: 102 people (accounting for 34%) buy fashion products from brand distributors.

Kol's consignment warehouse: 89 people (accounting for 29.7%) purchased fashion products from Kols consignment warehouses.

Buy from friends/relatives: 67 people (accounting for 22.3%) buy fashion products from friends or relatives.

Others: 1 person (accounting for 0.3%) has another shopping method that is not included in the above options.

Figure 8. Online fashion shopping channel

Source: Survey results

Regarding shopping for fashion online, **“Yes”** 264 people (accounting for 88%) have ever shopped for fashion online. This shows that **online shopping is a popular method** and is chosen by many people; **“No”** 35 people (accounting for 11.7%) do not shop for fashion online, maybe they prefer to shop directly at the store or have personal reasons for not choosing online shopping; **“Yes but not often”** 1 person (accounting for 0.3%).

Figure 9: Favorite online shopping channel

Source: Survey results

Based on the survey results about online fashion shopping platforms that 265 participants participated in, the results show that:

Shopee: 234 people (accounting for 88.3%) like to shop for fashion through the Shopee platform. Shopee is one of the popular and popular online shopping platforms in Vietnam.

Instagram: 152 people (accounting for 57.4%) Likes to shop for fashion via Instagram. Instagram is often a platform for fashion brands to share their latest products and information.

Facebook: 128 people (accounting for 48.3%) like to shop for fashion via Facebook. Facebook offers many shopping groups and online stores for users.

Lazada: 103 people (accounting for 38.9%) like toshop for fashion through the Lazada platform. Lazada is also one of the famous online shopping platforms in Vietnam.

Tiki: 81 people (accounting for 30.6%) like to shop for fashion through Tiki. Tiki is also one of the popular online shopping platforms in Vietnam.

Zalo: 54 people (accounting for 20.4%) shop for fashion via Zalo. Zalo also provides several online stores for users.

Others: 12 people (accounting for 4.5%) Prefer other online fashion shopping platforms that are not on the list above.

Box 2. Online fashion shopping

Many domestic and foreign brands have been applying to sell clothes online and earn high profits. There are also countless values that online business has truly brought.

Consumers are gradually feeling “LAZY” to shop, lazy to go to the store and if they don’t have the clothes they want, they will be very frustrated. Therefore, shopping for clothes online can be an effective option.

One of the leading brands in the retail fashion industry, clothing accounts for 43% of items purchased mainly online in recent years.

Source: gosell.vn (2023)

Figure 10: Consultation and product purchase links from Beauty Bloggers/KOLs

Source: Survey results

Consultation and product purchase links of Beauty Bloggers/KOLs, with 300 survey participants:

There were 186 people (accounting for 62%) who often consulted and purchased product links from Beauty Bloggers/KOLs. It shows that **Beauty Bloggers/KOLs have a great influence on**

users' choice to buy fashion products. Not consulting only 114 people (accounting for 38%) do not often consult opinions and product purchase links from Beauty Bloggers/KOLs.

Box 3. Vietnam KOL in the fashion field (Fashion)

Chau Bui: One of the pioneering names in the Fashionista world is Chau Bui. She constantly updates her style when appearing at fashion weeks, influential events in the world.

Quynh Anh Shyn: Transforming from Hot girl to being welcomed to famous fashion events. Quynh Anh Shyn increasingly asserts herself through unique, individual outfits.

Coem Trendy: Khanh Linh, also known as Co em Trendy, has become a familiar name to young fashion lovers with her liberal, modern style.

Source: *cleverads.vn* (2023)

Figure 11: Monthly amount of money young people spend on fashion

Source: Survey results

Regarding the monthly amount of money surveyed young people are willing to spend on fashion, the results show:

Under 500 thousand VND: 60 people (accounting for 20%) often choose to buy fashion products priced under 500 thousand VND.

From 500 thousand VND to 1 million VND: 68 people (accounting for 22.7%) often choose to buy fashion products in the price range from 500 thousand VND to 1 million VND. **This is the amount that young people can afford to pay the most in a month.**

From 1 million VND to 1.5 million VND: 51 people (accounting for 17%) often choose to buy fashion products in the price range from 1 million VND to 1.5 million VND.

From 1.5 million VND to 2 million VND: 31 people (accounting for 10.3%) often choose to buy fashion products in the price range from 1.5 million VND to 2 million VND.

From 2 million VND to 3 million VND: 23 people (accounting for 7.7%) often choose to buy fashion products in the price range from 2 million VND to 3 million VND.

From 3 million VND to 4 million VND: 11 people (accounting for 3.7%) often choose to buy fashion products in the price range from 3 million VND to 4 million VND.

From 4 million VND to 5 million VND: 44 people (accounting for 14.7%) often choose to buy fashion products in the price range from 4 million VND to 5 million VND.

Above 5 million VND: 12 people (accounting for 4%) often choose to buy fashion products costing over 5 million VND.

Figure 12: Fashion style

Source: Survey results

Regarding the current fashion style that young people are aiming for:

Classic Style: 83 people (accounting for 27.7%) prefer classic and traditional fashion styles.

Minimalism Style: 153 people (accounting for 51%) prefer minimalist, simple and uncomplicated fashion style.

Hippie Style: 157 people (accounting for 52.3%) prefer a free, natural and unconstrained fashion style. **This is the style chosen by many young people.**

Bohemian Style: 61 people (accounting for 20.3%) favor nomadic fashion style, expressing freedom and creativity.

Sport Style: 133 people (accounting for 44.3%) prefer sporty, dynamic and comfortable fashion styles.

Preppy Style: 110 people (accounting for 36.7%) prefer student, traditional and polite fashion styles.

Normcore Style: 68 people (accounting for 22.7%) prefer simple and non-special fashion styles.

Vintage Style: 108 people (accounting for 36%) prefer classic, vintage and historical fashion styles.

Hypebeast: 35 people (accounting for 11.7%) prefer hyped fashion style, following the latest trends.

Luxury: 36 people (accounting for 12%) prefer high-end, expensive and luxurious fashion styles.

Others: 6 people (accounting for 2%) prefer other fashion styles not on the list above.

Figure 13: The origin of fashion products is often chosen.

Source: Survey results

Regarding the trend of favoring fashion styles according to country origin:

Korea: in the third place with 146 people (accounting for 48.7%) favoring fashion styles from Korea, especially K-Fashion.

Japan: 101 people (accounting for 33.7%) favor fashion styles originating from Japan, such as J-Fashion.

Europe: 116 people (accounting for 38.7%) favor fashion styles from European countries, such as France, Italy, Spain, and many others.

Vietnam: 222 people (accounting for 74%) favor fashion styles originating from Vietnam, reflecting the trend of prioritizing diversity and developing domestic fashion. **Currently, young people are still choosing “Made in Vietnam” products as the biggest choice in this survey.**

Box 4. Vietnamese fashion “takes the throne.”

In recent years, many famous “Made in Vietnam” fashion brands have appeared in the province such as Canifa, Viet Tien, Owen, Aristino, Elise, NEM, Ivy moda, Yody, Savani, F5 Fashion... with high quality. Good product quality and reasonable prices have attracted consumers. The presence of “Made in Vietnam” fashion brands meets the needs of many people and affirms the position of Vietnamese fashion in the current period.

With product quality and reasonable prices, “Made in Vietnam” fashion brands have met the needs of most people and affirmed the position of Vietnamese fashion in the current period.”

Source: vietnam.vn (2023)

China: **In the second place** with 150 people (accounting for 50%) favoring fashion styles originating from China, especially modern Chinese style.

America: 100 people (accounting for 33.3%) favor fashion styles originating from America, such as American street style.

UK: 60 people (accounting for 20%) favor fashion styles originating from the UK, such as British fashion.

Others: 5 people (accounting for 1.7%) prefer fashion styles from other countries not on the list above.

Figure 14: Factors affecting the choice of fashion products.

Source: Survey results

Personal preference factor has the biggest influence on fashion choice, followed by tastes, culture, trends, tastes, opinions of others and KOLs... specifically:

Personal preference: 263 people (accounting for 87.7%) favor and choose fashion based on personal preferences. They often buy fashion products that they like and that suit their own style.

Tastes and culture: 149 people (accounting for 49.7%) favor and choose fashion based on taste and culture, they follow fashion trends and styles that are popular in the society or cultural group to which they belong.

TREND: 145 people (accounting for 48.3%) favor and choose fashion based on trends, they pursue and buy fashion products that are hot and popular at the moment.

Opinions and comments of others: 113 people (accounting for 37.7%) favor and choose fashion based on the opinions and comments of others. They tend to choose products that are positively reviewed or recommended by others to buy.

KOL (Key Opinion Leaders): 69 people (accounting for 23%) favor and choose fashion based on the opinions and recommendations of KOLs, influential people in the fashion field and highly appreciated by the public.

Not influential: 1 person (accounting for 0.3%) said that influencing factors do not have a significant impact on their fashion shopping decisions.

Figure 15: Trends in using fashion products.

Source: Survey results

Regarding important factors when choosing fashion for 300 participants, we have the following results:

Express individuality:197 people (accounting for 65.7%) rated that expressing individuality is important when choosing fashion, they prefer clothes and accessories that reflect their own personality and style.

Natural beauty:190 people (accounting for 63.3%) rated that natural beauty is important when choosing fashion, they prefer clothes and accessories that honor naturalness and simplicity.

Neat and quick:182 people (accounting for 60.7%) rated that the quick factor is important when choosing fashion, they like products that are easy to wear and coordinate quickly and conveniently.

Polite:181 people (accounting for 60.3%) rated that politeness is important when choosing fashion, they prefer formal and polite outfits and accessories.

Comprehensive:178 people (accounting for 59.3%) rated that the comprehensive factor is important when choosing fashion, they choose outfits that are complete and suitable for each occasion and situation.

Arbitrary, not certain:1 person (accounting for 0.3%) said they choose fashion arbitrarily, without following a certain rule.

Freestyle:1 person (accounting for 0.3%) said the comfort factor is important when choosing fashion, they prefer comfortable and pleasant clothes and accessories.

Table 1. Aspects that are considered when buying fashion products

Unit of measure: Person

Aspects that are considered	1. Very uninte rested	2. Unint ereste d	3. Norma l	4. Intere sted	5. Very inter ested	Avera ge score	Evaluation level
Origin of products	9	13	50	115	113	4.03	<i>Interested</i>
Price of the product	5	4	21	148	122	4.26	Very interested
Quality of the product	4	3	21	157	115	4.25	Very interested
<i>Design and model of the product</i>	3	3	19	124	151	4.39	<i>Very interested</i>
Promotions, discounts...	3	4	35	134	124	4.24	Very interested
Environmental friendliness	8	13	49	114	116	4.06	<i>Interested</i>
Customer care service	3	7	43	134	113	4.16	<i>Interested</i>
<i>A neat appearance</i>	5	2	18	121	154	4.39	<i>Very interested</i>
The most authentic language	4	8	37	159	92	4.09	Interested

of the wearer							
Respect for yourself and others	3	5	19	155	118	4.27	Very interested
Help yourself become more confident	5	0	16	129	149	4.38	Very interested

Convention: 1. Very uninterested; 2. Uninterested; 3. Normal; 4. Interested; 5. Very interested

Source: Compiled and calculated by the research team

Regarding the survey participants' Interested aspects when buying fashion, ranked in order from highest to lowest score, it shows:

Design and model of the product: Average score of 4.39, survey participants rated it as "Very interested."

A neat appearance: Average score of 4.39, survey participants rated it as "Very interested" for a neat appearance.

Help yourself become more confident: Average score of 4.38, survey participants rated it as "Very interested" towards fashion helps to feel more confident.

Respect for yourself and others: With an average score of 4.27, survey participants rated "Very interested" in showing respect for themselves and others through fashion.

Price of the product: With an average score of 4.26, survey participants rated "Very interested" in the product's price.

Quality of the product: With an average score of 4.25, survey participants rated "Very interested" in the quality of the product.

Promotions, discounts...: With an average score of 4.24, survey participants rated it as "Very interested" in promotions, discounts...

Customer care service: With an average score of 4.16, survey participants rated "Interested" for customer service.

The most authentic language of the wearer: With an average score of 4.09, survey participants rated "Interested" for the wearer's choice of the most authentic language.

Environmental friendliness: With an average score of 4.06, survey participants rated the product as "Interested" for the environmental friendliness of the product.

Origin of products: With an average score of 4.03, survey participants rated the product's origin as "Interested".

Figure 16: Young people's views on some judgments when consuming fashion products

Source: Survey results

Regarding agreement and disagreement with opinions related to fashion, the majority of young people disagree with these statements, or this is considered as ***There are some misconceptions in fashion consumption that need to be kept in mind to avoid making them.*** In which:

The more expensive the clothes, the better: There are 58 people (accounting for 19.3%) who agree with this opinion, while 242 people (accounting for 80.7%) disagree. Most people disagree that the more expensive the clothes, the better.

Colorful clothes are only suitable for young people: There are 49 people (accounting for 16.3%) who agree and 251 people (accounting for 83.7%) who disagree. Most people do not agree that colorful clothes are only suitable for young people.

Men's clothing is just for men: There are 96 people (accounting for 32%) who agree and 204 people (accounting for 68%) who disagree. Most people disagree that men's clothing is only for men.

You must be tall to look good in clothes: There are 78 people (accounting for 26%) who agree and 222 people (accounting for 74%) who disagree. Most people do not agree that you must be tall to look good in clothes.

Combine many types of patterns for beauty: There are 71 people (accounting for 23.7%) agree and 229 people (accounting for 76.3%) disagree. Most people do not agree that combining many patterns is the way to look beautiful.

Choose colors that match the weather: There are 118 people (accounting for 39.3%) who agree and 182 people (accounting for 60.7%) who disagree. Most people agree that choosing colors should match the weather.

To be fashionable, have to follow the trend: 71 people (accounting for 23.7%) agree and 229 people (accounting for 76.3%) disagree. Most people do not agree that if you want to be stylish, you have to follow trends.

Old clothes are thrown away: There are 45 people (accounting for 15%) who agree and 255 people (accounting for 85%) who disagree. Most people do not agree that old clothes are thrown away.

Never wear again: There are 53 people (accounting for 17.7%) who agree and 247 people (accounting for 82.3%) who disagree. Most people disagree that they should never wear it again.

Box 5. Some notes when consuming fashion

According to *tokenh14.vn (2018)* 5 lessons: (i) Understand the body shape: “show off beauty and hide ugliness”; (ii) Not paying too much attention to branded products; (iii) Fashion inspiration is everywhere; (iv) Prioritize items that are both comfortable and still attractive; (v) Choose items that make you feel confident and comfortable.

According to *Eve Nguyen (2015)* Misconceptions about fashion that people easily have: (i) The more expensive the clothes, the better; (ii) Must dress according to body shape; (iii) The age to wear colorful clothes is over; (iv) Men’s clothing is just for men; (v) Only tall makes you beautiful; (vi) Don’t combine multiple patterns; (vii) Choose colors that match the weather; (viii) To be fashionable, have to follow the trend; (ix) Old clothes are trash

5. SOME EXCHANGES AND DISCUSSIONS

Fashion is a field rich in potential because market demand is always stable. The number of fashion enthusiasts is very large (70.7% according to survey results), so the fashion market is still fertile ground for investors. Investing in the fashion industry is very competitive, investors also need to be interested in building their own brand.

It can be seen that building a fashion brand is a vital factor if want to do business in this field. Fashion brands will help businesses become strong if they correctly identify potential customers and ensure synchronization and consistency of brand identity elements. Of course, other factors such as product quality, price, customer care policy also need to be considered. This is a persistent process to be recognized and trusted by customers.

The factor of personal preference has the greatest influence on the survey subjects’ fashion choices. Customers for businesses are considered a springboard for the long-term development of the business and the ultimate goal that most businesses aim for. Therefore, capturing all emotions, thoughts and customer needs as accurately as possible is always an important task that must be done. Fashion is a field with an extremely competitive market, especially with the trend of opening up economic integration. Therefore, it forces shop owners and companies to identify their target customers most accurately. Thanks to that, you will better understand your customers as well as your target market and build marketing and sales strategies with the highest optimal conversion rate. It is very difficult for businesses to increase revenue if they do not know who their target customers are.

According to survey results, online fashion shopping is chosen by young people at a large rate. Therefore, online fashion business is one of the solutions to help promote and develop revenue effectively. A business that can effectively promote its brand promotion capabilities, as well as provide customer care and support and give customers the best experience when they visit the store’s website, will expand its market and enhance its brand will take place.

About the online fashion sales process needed: (i) Choose online fashion products suitable for customer segments; (ii) Analyze the market and competitors in the fashion industry; (iii) Choose an online fashion business channel; (iv) Deploy marketing strategies; (v) Consulting and customer care. The transformation of digital and technology forces the fashion industry to change. Consumption patterns, digital marketing channels and strategies, and production methods are constantly changing every day.

KOL (Key Opinion Leader) Currently plays a very important role in building and developing fashion brands for businesses in Vietnam. Using KOL Marketing to promote products, fashion businesses will also easily reach the exact target customer base, build customer trust and increase

interaction between the two parties. The larger the number of KOL followers, the greater the brand's reach to customers. Therefore, fashion businesses should also consider KOL engagement with their followers. A quality KOL will interact a lot with followers, post quality articles, videos, answer audience questions...

The proportion of survey subjects choosing Vietnamese fashion accounting for is the highest in choosing fashion products associated with product origin. The transformation and rise of Vietnamese fashion with diverse designs and high-quality products has contributed to the success of the Campaign "Vietnamese people prioritize using Vietnamese products". Along with an increasingly solid position in the market, domestic garment manufacturers need to continue to research, quickly grasp world fashion trends and produce products suitable for many ages at reasonable prices, and at the same time organize promotional and super promotional programs to stimulate shopping demand and affirm the "Made in Vietnam" fashion brand in the market.

Regarding the aspects that are interested in buying fashion by survey participants, they show that they are most interested in "Product design and style", "A neat appearance". Therefore, to increase competitiveness with foreign fashion, Vietnamese fashion businesses must invest in market research, grasp consumer trends and anticipate the fashion styles of Vietnamese customers in all segments: popular - middle - high-end segment and target men, women, young people, middle-aged people...

Conclusion

The fashion market is human beauty trends. Fashion business today attracts a lot of attention from many people. Human life is increasingly improved and enhanced, so human needs are also growing more and more. One of the increasingly demanding areas of people is the requirements for the fashion market. In today's ever-changing environment, human needs are increasing, so the demands of the fashion industry are also growing. The research article has provided some additional evidence about the fashion trends of Vietnamese generation Z youth today.

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